

Keep the Conversations Going: Engagement-Based Customer Segmentation

on

Online Social Service Platforms

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CERTIFICATE

It is certified that the dissertation work titled “**Keep the Conversations Going: Engagement-Based Customer Segmentation on Online Social Service Platforms**” by **Mr. Nripesh Trivedi** (Roll No. 11412EN001) for the award of the degree of *Master of Technology (Integrated) in Mathematics and Computing* has been supervised/examined by me. This work has not been submitted for the award of any other degree/diploma. It is certified that the report embodies the results of the work carried out by him within the prescribed period.

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Where a Linear Separation of the Data Exists. Reprinted with permission from (Kim, 2013)

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Most businesses and organizations develop online services as a value-added offering, which is a significant revenue stream from their existing user base. Such services may be enhanced with social features to serve as value-added tools for user attraction and retention. Social features may allow users to be able to post content, share information and directly interact with each other. However, if these online social features do not engage users effectively, the likelihood of users churning to a competitor increases. It is, therefore, important to identify and understand the degree to which users of online social services (OSS) can be engaged using these available online social features. For this purpose, this thesis presents a methodological framework for identifying non-overlapping segments of users by the way they engage with an OSS platform. It argues why the traditional k -means approach for user segmentation is ill-suited when social features on an OSS platform with large data sets are considered, and advocates for the integration of kernel functions into segmenting, identifying and understanding user engagement profiles. This framework is demonstrated with real data on user activities on a large scale OSS.

Online services created and managed by organizations offer novel, value-added services for its users. Such services improve a customer's loyalty to a brand (Ogonowski et al., 2014) and discourages them from churning to a competitor (Harris and Goode, 2004). Archetypical examples of online services include online health portals by medical clinics that show patient lab results and other health related information (Gummerus et al., 2004), peer-review and rating systems for e-business and auction websites, and insurance portals that let users search for resources where a policy is eligible for use. Organizations may even be entirely dependent on their online service offerings for revenue (Chuang et al., 2014). For example, organizations running web search engines, video streaming sites, online social networks, and news publishing sites rely on users to utilize their online service and view advertisements or register for subscriptions to generate revenue.

An emerging body of research suggests that the integration of social elements into online services yield a positive effect on purchase intention and brand loyalty, and that the extensive use of such features encourages users to continue to return to the service (Chen et al., 2013; Cyr et al., 2007; Huang and Benyoucef, 2013). Online services featuring social elements, hereafter referred to as an *online social service* (OSS), may use designs that let users share information and interact with each other directly. For example, Amazon.com has a feature that lets users not only rate the product they buy, but also leave a subjective review that yields insights on the product's value. Other website visitors may subsequently rate the quality and helpfulness of this review.

Organizations that are able to study and quantify the ways in which users experience engagement in their online services, defined as a quality of the user experience that emphasizes the effects of positive aspects of interaction (Attfield and Kazai, 2011), stands to gain a market advantage. For example, engagement analysis could separate users who choose to use only specific aspects of an

online service, and who exhibit patterns similar to those who had left the service and never returned. Such analysis may be used to build models that predict user churn based on engagement features. Engagement analysis may further highlight parts of the service that are negatively associated with user engagement or is seldom used by users who do exhibit high engagement. Organizations could also use it to evaluate the total effectiveness of social features. For example, a social widget with which only a small percentage of users are engaged suggests the need to re-evaluate its design and functionality. This could be an indicator for eliminating or redesigning such facets of the service. The degree to which a user experiences engagement with respect to social features thus requires careful consideration.

Engagement is an inherently qualitative concept, and most present day approaches measure this using user surveys or other self-reporting mechanisms (Lalmas et al., 2013). Self-reported, qualitative measures of engagement are not desirable because the analysis is only limited to users who are willing to participate in a survey. Since different analysts may hold two different interpretations, that could lead to conflicting measurements and recommendations. An improved measure would be one that: (i) relies on user and behavioral features that are captured as users engage with the OSS; (ii) aggregates the readings of such features across all users into a big data set; and (iii) partitions users into groups according to these features in an automatic, unsupervised way with a minimum number of analyst defined hyper-parameters.

Using a big dataset from an active OSS, this article presents a framework involving the use of kernel k -means clustering to segment users by their social features. The framework operationalizes multiple dimensions of user engagement through the recorded activities of users and the social features they use. It classifies a user into profiles that summarize the way and the degree to which he or she engages with the OSS. Traditional k -means clustering is a long-

standing and widely used approach to identify and segment users based on their behavior (Chang et al., 2007). However, in our framework, kernel k -means is proposed as an unsupervised clustering algorithm since data distributions related to social interactions are typically skewed or heavy-tailed, and hence, requires a kernel function to map the data to a higher dimensional space where one can find linear separations irrespective of skewness.

CHAPTER 2
LITERATURE REVIEW

Studying the engagement of a person who participates in an activity is a research process that is based on the researcher's definition of what it means "to be engaged" and the context in which engagement is studied. A near universal trait, however, is to first define features that characterize the "engagement behaviors" of a person as it relates to the interactions he or she performs in the activity. One body of work considers physiological measures for this purpose (Ikehara and Crosby, 2005; Konradt and Sulz, 2001; Seah and Cairns, 2008). The physiological data may come from sensors like eye trackers, mouse movements, blood pressure, heart pulses, and cameras (Attfield and Kazai, 2011) and measure features such as eye movements, heart rate, and mouse clicks. Such analysis reveals bodily reactions that are cognitively linked to mental engagement in a task. However, mental engagement is not easily relatable in the context of user analytics. For example, it is not feasible to measure the physiological state of large numbers of users as they interact with an OSS, and even if it were possible, it may be difficult to interpret into actionable insights.

Analysis of engagement with respect to user interactions are more practical to perform because it does not depend on physiological readings. Furthermore, since user interactions are based on the functionality and interface of a platform, the engagement analysis may lead to actionable insights for the platform owner. Previous research has proposed a variety of measures for quantifying or measuring user interactions for this purpose. The most popular approaches involve self-reporting, where questionnaires, interviews, reports, and product reaction cards are given to users in the hope that they respond honestly (Lalmas et al., 2013). For example, Webster and Ho (1997) developed a seven item questionnaire with items that include the degree of attention, challenge, intrinsic interest, and variety in the context of presentation software. Jacques (1996) developed a 13-item survey to evaluate user engagement in online e-commerce environments.

His survey included items about user's attention, perceived time, motivation, needs, control, and attitudes. In practice, Brooke (1996) addresses the functionality of a system and users' satisfaction of those systems. Previous studies has used this technology independent test to assess user engagement in hardware, software and web systems. Self-reported measures of engagement carry few technological hurdles to adopt and are relatively cheap to run (Gagné and Godin, 2005; Hawkshead and Krousel-Wood, 2007), but they are inherently subjective and their analysis may be limited by the number of participants involved (Lalmas et al., 2013).

Rather than asking users to self-report, emerging approaches seek to measure user behaviors directly from a software system. Depending on the software, analysts may define various key behavioral indicators (KBIs) and their relationship to user engagement. Media websites, for example, may use average page views, bounce rate (people arriving at a website and leaving immediately), user satisfaction, and top internal search phrases as different types of KBIs. An e-commerce website may use a different set of KBIs, such as conversion rates (ratio of users who buy an item), average order value, and user loyalty metrics (Booth and Jansen, 2008). By themselves, KBIs reveal the engagement characteristics of an individual user. Recent work has considered how the collection of all KBIs across all users may be used to build models that classify users into broad segments, each corresponding to a different mode or type of engagement profile. For example, Lehmann et al., (2012) considered similar user interactions that were performed across a variety of different websites, from social media to e-commerce, to discover a small number of Web user engagement profiles (Lehmann et al., 2012). Their study considered users grouped a priori into different segments based on the number of days in a month a user visited the website. van Dam and van de Velden, (2014) consider different features of Facebook users to classify them into different types. However, the features used for building

engagement models are specific to the system that is under consideration, with little guidance as to how their approach may be generalized or adapted to work within a different context.

Although the present art in engagement analysis focuses on the KBIs of individual systems. Generalizing KBI-based approaches to any online platform, however, is not realistic since the KBIs used in each study vary widely and are platform specific. Instead, this thesis proposes a framework for engagement analysis that is applicable to any type of OSS. To ensure broad applicability, the approach generalizes notions of engagement through multiple abstract dimensions into application-specific KBIs can be classified.

CHAPTER 3
ENGAGEMENT ANALYSIS
FRAMEWORK

In this section, our framework is introduced for segmenting customers based on the way they engage on an OSS. We first consider how to summarize the notion of engagement along three orthogonal dimensions, and discuss the types of user behaviors that embody each dimension. Then the heavy-tailed characteristic of the distributions of these features is presented and why traditional k -means clustering is unsuitable is discussed. As part of the case study, a framework is presented in which kernel k -means clustering is introduced as a method better suited to handle heavy-tailed online social features.

3.1 Dimensions of Engagement

Instead of basing engagement analysis on specific platform interactions, a breakdown of the concept is proposed into multiple generic dimensions that KBIs germane to any OSS may be associated with (Lehmann et al., 2012). These dimensions are:

- (i) *Initiation*: This describes how often a user chooses to enter the service, and once she is on how frequently she initiates a social action. It captures the notion that engaged users are more likely to access the service often, and once they have logged in, have a tendency to perform many subsequent actions.
- (ii) *Interaction*: This describes the volume of social interactions a user performs, emphasizing the utilization of the platform's social elements. For example, users who often upload content or share their thoughts, frequently respond and react to content posted by others, or establish virtual ties with a large number of other may be highly engaged.
- (iii) *Loyalty*: This reflects the length of time for which a user has actively participated on the service. Large mean number of logins per day, short lengths of times

between logins, and long active sessions may reflect users who are active over a long period and hence is a faithful user of the social service.

The KBIs (hereafter referred to as user or behavioral features) best reflecting each of these dimensions depend on the type of online service, the kinds of social elements available on it, and the type of recorded user behavior data.

3.2 Segmenting Users by Engagement

After n behavioral features across all of above dimensions are identified for a platform, the next task is to segment each user into an engagement vector \mathbf{x} . A natural way of segmenting users based on their engagement activities is to utilize a clustering algorithm that separates the set of vectors $\{\mathbf{x}\}$ into non-overlapping groups based on a measure of vector distance or similarity. For this purpose, most studies turn to k -means clustering, a simple algorithm often used for user behavior modeling (Farajian and Mohammadi, 2010). It identifies a collection of k (specified a priori) centroid vectors \mathbf{c}_j in the feature space, and assigns vectors to classes by the centroid vector it is closest to. The optimal set of k centroid positions \mathbf{C}_k are those that minimize the sum of all distances from the engagement vectors to their assigned centroids:

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \min_{\{e_m \in \mathbf{C}_k\}} \sum_{m=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| \mathbf{x}_i^{(j)} - e_m \right\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where k is specified a priori and $\sum_{m=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| \mathbf{x}_i^{(j)} - e_m \right\|^2$ is the squared Euclidian distance between an engagement vector \mathbf{x}_i and the centroid e_m of its assigned cluster m . Note that the resulting assignment of data points to clusters define linear boundaries between points that fall into different clusters in the feature space (Jain, 2010). An iterative algorithm is typically used to find the set of centroids \mathbf{C}_k minimizing Equation (1):

1. Randomly choose k points in the space of all data vectors to serve as centroids.

2. Assign each vector \mathbf{x} to the group that has the closest centroid.
3. When all objects have been assigned, recalculate the k centroid positions.
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until the change in centroids between iterations fall below a threshold, Δ .

However, the set of engagement vectors across all users $\{\mathbf{x}\}$ needs to satisfy specific requirements for k -means to be applicable. In particular, all behavioral features represented in \mathbf{x} must exhibit similarly small variance so that the position of a centroid is not heavily influenced by outlier points. This is because k -means clustering can only identify linear separations in the data that may be impossible to find when one dimension of the data exhibits significant variance or large numbers of outliers (Shukla and Naganna, 2014). Such a variance requirement may not be satisfied for the social behavioral features of an OSS; countless past studies have shown how features related to social behaviors on online services follow heavy-tailed distributions. A heavy-tailed distribution is one whose complementary cumulative distribution function, $R(X) = \Pr(X > x)$, drops at a rate slower than exponential, i.e. when:

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} e^{sX} R(X) = \infty$$

This slow decay in the right tail of the distribution causes a significant variation in X . A particular type of heavy-tailed distribution is one that has a *power-tail*, where $R(X)$ satisfies the above limit and has the functional form:

$$R(X) = cX^{-\alpha}$$

where c is some constant and α is a scaling parameter. Power-tailed distributions exhibit even more variance than heavy-tailed ones, so much so that that all of its moments greater than $[\alpha]$ is infinite (Lipsky, 2009). For example, the sample distribution of a power-tailed random variable

with $\alpha < 2$ carries an infinite variance, and at $\alpha < 1$ an infinite mean. Table 1 illustrates how a wide variety of user behaviors on OSSs, as reported in previous research, exhibit heavy-tails. The table lists the specific heavy-tailed distribution that was observed.

Table 1: Heavy-Tailed Distributions in the Social Behaviors of Different OSS Services

Behavioral Feature	Online Social Service and Best Distribution Fit
Number of social connections	Facebook; heavy tailed (Ugander, Karrer, Backstrom, Marlow and Alto, 2011) Political blogs; log-normal (Adamic and Glance, 2005) Flickr; power law (Mislove et al., 2008) LiveJournal; power law (Viswanath et al., 2009) Orkut; power law (Viswanath et al., 2009) YouTube; power law (Viswanath et al., 2009) Google+; power law (Gong et al., 2012) Pinterest; power law (Zhong et al., 2014) GitHub; power law (Lima et al., 2014) Twitter: power law (Kwak et al., 2010)
Number of responses to a user contribution	Flickr; power law (Mislove et al., 2008) Pinterest; power law (Zhong et al., 2014) GitHub; power law (Lima et al., 2014) Twitter; power law (Kwak et al., 2010) Online games; power law (Szell and Thurner, 2010)
Session duration	Orkut; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) MySpace; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) Orkut; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) Hi5; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009)
Number of other users a user sends messages to	Slashdot; power law (Kunegis et al., 2009) StackOverflow; power law (Anderson et al., 2012) Online games; power law (Szell and Thurner, 2010)
Time between logins	Orkut; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) MySpace; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) Orkut; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009) Hi5; heavy-tailed (Benevenuto et al., 2009)
Frequency of logins	MySpace; right-skewed (Torkjazi et al., 2009)

In order to mitigate the negative effect of heavy-tailed data on the practical, yet even distribution of data into separate segments, some studies standardize feature values so that they all fall within

the same range, transforming the features to exhibit smaller variations and hence make them become more amenable to k -means clustering (Chu et al., 2009). This method, however, is a dangerous practice because empirical observations of heavy-tailed data may have points whose value is many times larger than the mean (Lipsky, 2009), causing a standardization to map the vast majority of points to a very small interval that does not reflect true differences in data point values.

3.3 Kernel k -means Clustering

To overcome these limitations of k -means, incorporation of a kernel function is introduced that projects data vectors into a higher dimensional space where the data is clustered. Intuitively, data that lives in a higher dimensional space has additional directions in which it varies, thus increasing the likelihood of finding a linear separation in the data. A simple illustration of this idea is shown in Figure 1

**Figure 1: Projection From a Lower Dimension (left) to a Higher (right) Dimensional Space
Where a Linear Separation of the Data Exists. Reprinted with permission from (Kim,
2013)**

In the left panel, points are shaped and colored by their true class (cluster) label, with no way to define a linear boundary between the two classes that k -means attempts to find. If we were to project that same data to a higher three-dimensional space using the transformation $(x, y) \rightarrow (x, y, x^2 + y^2)$, as shown in the right panel of Figure 1, however, we now see the linear separation that k -means can identify to correctly cluster the groups.

The kernel k -means algorithm applies k -means clustering to vectors that have been mapped to a higher dimensional space. It seeks a set C_k of k centroid positions satisfying a slightly modified version of Equation 1:

$$C_k = \underset{\{e_m \in C_k\}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{n|e_m|} \sum_{x_i \in E_m, x_j \in E_m} k(x_i, x_j) \quad (2)$$

where $k(x_i, x_j)$ is a kernel function that measures the distance (i.e. similarity) between two engagement vectors x_i and x_j assigned to the same cluster E_m with centroid e_m in some higher dimensional space. Different choices for the kernel function k encode different ways to perform the data projection. Many choices of kernel functions are possible, and the proposed framework considers the Gaussian radial basis function (RBF) kernel:

$$k(x_i, x_j) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where σ is a scaling hyper-parameter. The RBF kernel is an appropriate choice for cases in which there is little or no information available about how to project the data in a way that yields

a linear separation (Romero et al., 2014). It has been shown to perform well in a variety of contexts (De la Torre and Vinyals, 2007; Romero et al., 2014).

3.4 Hyper-Parameter Fitting

Both σ and k play a pivotal role in the performance of the kernel function. When σ is large, the exponential in the RBF kernel will take on a linear shape, and hence, will yield results similar to traditional k -means. On the contrary, if underestimated, the function may over fit the data set and hence yield a clustering result that is not generalizable to future users of the OSS. An analyst therefore needs to tune both k (the number of clusters to be used) and σ intuitively, using a measure of clustering quality to identify the best pair of parameter settings (Taniar, 2008).

Optimal hyper-parameter fitting is a long standing problem in machine learning (Bergstra and Bengio, 2012), and often requires an analyst to qualitatively compare the tradeoffs of different settings. In practice, an ideal set of parameter values should strongly discriminate points among clusters, that is, have points in the same cluster “close” to each other and points in different clusters “far” from each other. It should also be able to assign an equitable distribution of points into clusters. Strong discrimination ensures that each cluster represents a unique kind of engagement, while an equitable distribution offers insights that are more actionable.

To pinpoint a suitable value of k and σ , a combinations of values within a grid of feasible values is considered. We first measure how well a solution discriminates points among clusters using the silhouette (SI) coefficient, a typically used validation measure (Pang-Ning et al., 2006). It is defined by computing a scoring function s of the j^{th} data point assigned to the i^{th} cluster x_{ij} , taking the average of these scores across all points in a cluster, and then taking the average of these averages over all clusters (Kodinariya and Makwana, 2013):

$$S(k; \sigma) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m s(x_{ij}; \sigma) \quad (4)$$

The scoring function $s(x_{ij}; \sigma)$ for an RBF kernel requires a setting for the hyper-parameter σ and is given by (Camps-Valls et al., 2007):

$$s(x_{ij}; \sigma) = \frac{w^\ominus(x_j) - v^\ominus(x_j)}{\max(w^\ominus(x_j), v^\ominus(x_j))} \quad (5)$$

Where:

$$v^\ominus(x_j) = \frac{1}{(|C_i| - 1)} \kappa(x_j, x_j) - \frac{2}{(|C_i| - 1)} \sum_{x_j \in C_i, x_l \neq x_j} \kappa(x_j, x_l) + \frac{1}{(|C_i| - 1)} \sum_{x_l \in C_i, x_l \neq x_j} \kappa(x_l, x_l) \quad (6)$$

is the average distance from the projection of x_{ij} in a higher dimensional space to every other engagement vector assigned to the same cluster as x_j in the projected space, and:

$$w^\ominus(x_j) = \min_{h=1, \dots, i-1, i+1, \dots, k} \left(\frac{1}{(|C_h|)} \kappa(x_j, x_j) - \frac{2}{|C_h|} \sum_{x_l \in C_h} \kappa(x_j, x_l) + \frac{1}{|C_h|} \sum_{x_l \in C_h} \kappa(x_l, x_l) \right)_{\text{for } x_j \in C_i} \quad (7)$$

defines the average distance from x_j to every other engagement vector x_i that is not in the cluster to which x_j is assigned. Note that $s(x_{ij}; \sigma)$ will approach 1 as its distance to engagement vectors within clusters decreases. In the reverse, $s(x_{ij}; \sigma)$ will approach -1 as its distance to engagement vectors between clusters increases.

Out of the l parameter settings that yield $S(k; \sigma)$ values close to 1, a setting that has the most equitable distribution in terms of size of clusters is chosen. In our approach, we measure the equity of a distribution by the information theoretic concept of *entropy*, which is a way to quantify the “randomness” of a probability distribution. Intuitively, a skewed probability

distribution $p(x)$ is “less random” because its realizations often take a value with a skewed high frequency. However, a distribution where each value occurs with equal probability is “more random” in the sense that its multiple realizations are likely to yield a variety of values, and hence, it becomes difficult to predict the value of a random draw from it. The entropy of a probability distribution is defined as:

$$H[X] = -\sum_x p(x) \log_2 p(x) \quad (8)$$

where $p(x)$ is the probability that the random variable X takes on the value x . In this application, x corresponds to the cluster membership of a user and $p(x)$ is the probability that a randomly sampled user is a member of cluster x .

In summary, choosing the right parameters for both σ and k could be a daunting task. However, the intuitive hyper-parameter process explained above could help analysts come to a much quicker conclusion on identifying suitable values for both σ and k . This would help produce a set of clusters with an optimal number of clusters and size per each cluster for which businesses can make practical decisions. The result would also generate a set of clusters that on the one hand have high intra cluster similarity, yet on the other hand, have low inter cluster similarity.

A case study is presented to demonstrate our framework. It substantiates the utility of the kernel approach to segment users in a vibrant and active OSS service, and presents an engagement analysis along the three dimensions discussion earlier. The study contrasts the results of kernel k -means method against those obtained from the traditional k -means approach.

4.1 Platform and Data Description

The subject platform for the case study is an emerging OSS called *7 Cups of Tea (7cot)*. *7cot* fosters an active community of “listeners”, who are unpaid volunteers that are trained to support people facing a range of emotional problems. These listeners are able to connect with “members” (those that register on *7cot* to find support) through group chat, a vibrant forum, and one-on-one conversations. Members and listeners can recognize particularly helpful events that occur in either a private chat, group chat, or a forum, with badges and points awards. This noteworthiness is reflected in the profile of a user, thus increasing her reputation on the online service. The social aspects of the platform include connections between members and the listeners they communicate with, group chats defining relationships among participants, and forums that connect members across the user base by the threads in which they participate.

At the time of data collection, the OSS had attracted over 130,000 members and fostered over 1,270,000 one-on-one conversations. We accessed and utilized the entire collection of conversations for our study. Table 2 summarizes the participations and actions of the user base. The participation statistics underscore the size and volume of activities on *7cot*, while the action statistics reveal the average activity of a user during days when they have logged in at least once. For example, the table shows how members connect to an average of 1.83 listeners on the days they access *7cot*.

Identification of the ways and levels to which different users engage on 7cot is useful to find those who sparsely engage with the OSS, and hence should be targeted with promotions or exposed to marketing material that will promote their return to the service. Discovering the dimensions by which most users are not engaged also informs aspects of the social service that may not be fully utilized and inform how future iterations of the online service should be designed.

The set of active users was segmented with both traditional and kernel k -means clustering over a set of nine attributes. Table 3 presents a list of various types of user behaviors representative of each of the engagement dimensions discussed earlier in the thesis.

Table 2: Summary of 7cot User Participations and Actions

Participation		Actions (average per user per active day)	
Number of Conversations	1,270,000	Logins	2.41
Distinct Forums	53	Conversational Messages	62.28
Chatroom Messages	1,070,000	Conversational Requests	1.83
Forum Posts	82,223	Forum Posts	2.93
Number of Members	87,232	Forum Post Views	6.38
Number of Listeners	33,601	Page Views	15.98
Number of Hybrid	12,038	Help Guide Views	4.12

4.2 Kernel k -means Clustering

In the first phase of the analysis, a different clustering model using kernel k -means method was developed. As presented in Figure 2, the distributions of all the features were first explored in our data set to confirm if 7cot is a reasonable candidate for the application of a kernel k -means method. Figure 2 demonstrates that all the attributes are skewed, and exhibit a heavy-tailed shape. In each of the nine plots in the figure, the x axis represents the magnitude of a quantity while the y -axis represents the probability of the corresponding values of x is greater. The

smallest value of x after which a tail follows a power law distribution is labeled as x_{min} . The common approach to estimate this value is by visual inspection of the distribution on log-log scale. However, such an approach is highly subjective and prone to error. Clauset et al., (2009) provide a recommendation for estimating this lower threshold using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

Table 3: Dimensions and Attributes used for Clustering

Dimension	Attribute	Description
Initiation	Number of account logins (L)	Total number of times a user has logged into the website since they registered. It captures the idea that, the more frequently a user accesses the OSS, the more interested she may be in taking advantage of the site's services.
	Number of conversation requests (R)	Total number of times a user has requested a conversation from another user on the site. Conversation requests are a very strong form of interaction, with a user explicitly reaching out to connect to another person on the social service.
Interaction	Number of messages exchanged (M)	Total number of one-on-one, directed messages sent between users. It offers a direct insight into the extent to which a user is involved with other website users.
	Number of forum posts (P)	Total number of times a user has posted in the forum of the website since they registered. Intuitively, larger numbers of forum posts suggest that a user is experiencing strong site engagement.
	Number of forum views (V)	Total number of times a user has viewed the websites forum. This subtle feature captures the degree to which users are interested in the content shared on the service. The more the views, the more captured a user's interest is.
Loyalty	Number of help guide views (H)	Total number of times a user has viewed the help guide from the website for different problems. This depicts how much a user trusts the website's help resources.
	Number of page views from web (PW)	Total number of pages viewed by user surfing the website through web. This directly measures involvement of users who surf the web version.
	Number of page views from app (PA)	Total number of pages viewed by a user surfing the website through app. This directly measures involvement of users who surf the app version.

	Number of active days (A)	Total number of days that a user has logged into the website. This measures the user's loyalty. The greater the active days, the more loyal a user is.
--	---------------------------	--

Figure 2: Plots for heavy tailed distribution for the nine features as in Table 3

We use this approach to estimate and report the scaling parameter α and x_{min} in Table 4 for each of the nine features. Since the parameter alpha (α) lies between 2 and 3 for all but one feature, the mean exists but higher order moments for all but one feature are infinite.

Table 4: Power Law Parameters of Features Used

Feature	Parameter(α)	x_{min}
Account logins (L)	2.095	100
Forum posts (P)	2.417	95
Messages exchanged (M)	1.950	87
Conversation requests (R)	2.112	158
Forum views (V)	2.065	101
Help views (H)	2.101	101
Page views from web (PW)	2.077	101
Page views from app (PA)	2.076	98
Active days (A)	2.037	109

To build the clustering model using the kernel k -means method, we chose to vary the range of σ between 0.001 and 0.01. This is because, for values of σ above and below 0.01 and 0.001 respectively, solutions for any value of k undesirably placed the majority of points in just one or two clusters. Such a solution does not provide any actionable feedback, and hence is undesirable. We also limited the parameter k to be less than 7 so that users are not divided into a large number of small clusters that only represent a very specific behavior pattern exhibited by a small number of users. We also chose this number based on the practical number of business strategies and feedback initiatives that the business could undertake to encourage user engagement and decrease churning. Table 5 shows the SI values for different clustering solutions as k and σ vary.

It shows how smaller values of σ tend to yield results with smaller SI values. We show this trend in Figure 3 by specifically zooming into SI values for k values equal to 5 and 6.

Table 5: SI values for different assignments of k and σ

σ	$k=2$	$k=3$	$k=4$	$k=5$	$k=6$
0.001	0.077	0.092	0.126	0.029	0.029
0.003	0.095	0.135	0.149	0.166	0.145
0.005	0.074	0.138	0.127	0.167	0.177
0.007	0.122	0.097	0.141	0.184	0.196
0.009	0.074	0.153	0.146	0.175	0.190
0.01	0.074	0.151	0.170	0.193	0.199

The shape of the graph may be because, as the value of σ is lowered, the algorithm fails to compute reasonable linear separators with dropping values of σ . Likewise, it was found that σ values greater than 0.01 generates higher SI values. However, such a value of σ causes the attendant problem whereby the majority of users are clustered into just a few groups.

Table 6 lists the entropy of the cluster size distributions for all clustering solutions whose SI values are among the top five in Table 5. The top five were chosen heuristically noting in the present case that the SI values begins to steeply decrease beyond the fifth value. We subsequently search for the most actionable and intuitive solution, where for a practical number of clusters created, there was a relatively even distribution of data points in each cluster. It was

found that the parameter settings $k = 6$ and $\sigma = 0.009$ yields a distribution of users into clusters with the highest entropy, and hence, is a balanced solution.

Figure 3: SI values for $k=5$ and $k=6$ with different values for σ

Table 6: Entropy of the Top Five SI values in Table 5

Hyper-Parameter (σ)	K	SI Value	Entropy
0.001	5	0.193	1.243552
0.007	6	0.196	1.673561
0.009	6	0.190	1.682574
0.01	6	0.199	1.626085
0.007	5	0.184	1.250008

4.3. Traditional k -means Clustering

In the second phase of the case study analysis, a clustering model is developed using the traditional k -means clustering method. For this comparative analysis, multiple clustering models are built with different values of k as is shown in Table 7. As k was varied, we found that traditional k -means grouped majority of users in one cluster for all values of k . For example, Figure 4 visualizes the proportion of users falling into each cluster at $k=6$, where an SI value of 0.922 is achieved. Although this SI value is very promising, the skew seen in the distribution of users into clusters cannot support practical business decision making. For example, an interpretation of how 96.3% of all users on 7cot engage would be too broad and lack actionable insights when applied to such a large population of users. Furthermore, adapting an OSS strategy based on how a small fraction of its users engages may not be cost effective for the organization.

Figure 4: Distribution of Users Per Cluster Using Traditional k -means

Table 7: SI Values and Corresponding Entropy Values for Traditional k -means Clustering

SI Value	Entropy	<i>k</i>
0.983	0.024	2
0.973	0.027	3
0.971	0.054	4
0.945	0.124	5
0.922	0.186	6

4.4. Comparing Traditional and Kernel *k*-means

In this section, the results of using both traditional *k*-means and kernel *k*-means clustering algorithms were compared to analyze user engagement. Even though the traditional *k*-means method produced SIs that are more favorable, the distribution of cluster sizes generated are highly skewed. This makes for an impractical solution for most business applications. To further compare the quality of the traditional and kernel *k*-means clusters, we thus rely only partially on the SI values and more heavily on the entropy parameter (Steinbach et al., 2000) which quantifies the equity of users among clusters. As discussed in the hyper-parameter fitting section, since the entropy of a sample is directly proportional to its uniformity of spread across different segments, higher the entropy, more balanced the clustering solution is.

For a parsimonious comparative analysis that would utilize only consistent parameters, a range of cluster counts between 3 and 6 were considered for both the traditional and kernel *k*-means methods. Bearing the discussion in the hyper-parameter searching section for our choice of *k*, we deemed these cluster sizes as the most practicable and actionable for our target OSS in terms of the business strategy aligned with improving user engagement. Also, for the kernel *k*-means method, we chose a sigma value of 0.009 as was determined during the hyper parameter search.

As shown in Figure 5, the kernel k -means algorithm performs better than the traditional k -means algorithm for different values of k based on entropy values. Across all values of k , the average entropy value of the kernel k -means algorithm (1.33875) is greater than that of the traditional k -means algorithm (0.12275) by an approximate order of 10. For instance, the traditional k -means cluster distribution (for $k=6$) as shown in Figure 4 indicates that at least 96% of the users were grouped into just one cluster whereas the kernel k -means cluster distribution in Figure 6 shows a relatively even distribution with the largest cluster containing approximately 30% of the users.

Figure 5: Entropy Values for Kernel and Traditional k -means for Different Values of k

Figure 6: Distribution of Users Per Cluster Using Kernel k -means

4.5 Kernel k -means Findings: Engagement Analysis

In this section, the findings that were generated based on the kernel k -means algorithm and explain the dynamics of user segmentation in terms of their engagement activities on the OSS used in the case study.

Figure 7: Plot of Normalized Centroid Co-ordinates for All Features Grouped According to Their Respective Dimensions (Graph Legend is explained in Table 3)

In Figure 7, the normalized centroid coordinates were shown with respect to a particular feature. The features are also grouped into their respective dimensions. The largest group of users are in the fourth cluster. These users were termed as the VIP users of the website. Figure 7 also shows that users in cluster four rank high in all of the three key dimensions, initiation, interaction and loyalty. They are more engaged in the sense that, they log in and surf the website often, either using a web or a mobile version of the service. They also post messages, respond to other posted messages and generally engage in conversations with other users. We classify these VIP users as such because they essentially form the participant base of the platform and help maintain and popularize the functioning of the website.

The next group of users that were identified belong to the third cluster. In Figure 7, it is evident that the users in this cluster are high in terms of initiation and moderate in terms of interaction, while they are extremely low in terms of loyalty. These users tend to visit the website frequently and log in often. However, their participation is limited in terms of exchange of messages with other participants on the platform. We chose to term them as latent users because even though they have a lot of interest in the website, which their frequent logins demonstrate, their full

potential as loyal participants is not realized yet. That is, they have interest in the website yet, they probably do not interact extensively because there are not enough suitable functions on the platform that serve their need. They are at the borderline of fully engaging in the platform or completely churning if the OSS does not meet their interests in a timely manner. In a situation where the business wants to expand its participant-base, this latent group will be the most important group to target.

The last group of users that were identified belong to the remainder of the clusters: clusters one, two, five and six. This group of users were termed as the focused users. Based on Figure 7, we see that these users have no loyalty; neither do they initiate visits to the platform often. Their prime engagement with the platform is via the interaction dimension. It was also realized that these users send a lot of conversation request that results in a relatively high number of messages exchanged with other users. In reference to an earlier description of the platform, these users are “members” who utilize the free social services of the 7cot platform by seeking support from “listeners’ about their condition. This group of users are not necessarily the dominating participant base of the platform. However, they are very purposeful in terms of exact services they need from the platform. They have a niche interest, and hence not all the numerous functions on the platform would appeal to them. As a result, the business will have to identify the specific needs and interest of such a group of users.

Organizing data into sensible groups such that practical and informed actions can be taken is a basic component of any unsupervised learning methodology (Jain, 2010). Based on our analysis, it was demonstrated that kernel k -means algorithms are capable of capturing non-linear relationships between data points in a large data set, and hence highly useful for real world applications such as studying user engagement on OSS platforms (Chitta et al., 2014). By comparing one of the most widely used clustering methods, traditional k -means with kernel k -means, we show that the kernel algorithm produces relatively higher entropy values on average. This indicates that the kernel algorithm generates clusters that have relatively even uniformity in terms of cluster sizes as shown in Figure 6. For businesses and organizations who have online presence via OSS platforms, this allows for the deployment of practical and actionable analysis and decisions on how to improve user engagement and, hence reduce churning.

Being able to determine the number of clusters needed for any application using the kernel k -means approach could be a difficult experience that may requires both science and art. Based on our case study, a four-step approach was identified for determining the best cluster solution for a kernel k -means clustering analysis that is applicable to other business segmentation problems. First, we consider a practicable value for k based on the business application for such segmentation. Secondly, the hyper-parameter, σ was considered, which is most important factor that forms the basis of the kernel function utility. We liberally chose the value for σ such that at least 80 percent of the data points are grouped into at least two clusters. In our dataset, we found this value to be between 0.01 and 0.001. Next, we choose an SI value by picking the top few value after which there is a significant drop in the SI values. Lastly, we choose the most practical clustering solution by choosing a clustering solution with the highest entropy.

The engagement analysis framework provided a three-fold insight into the 7cot OSS. First, we are able to explore, understand and group features that influence the level of user engagement into three deferent dimensions. Secondly, with the aid of kernel k -means, we are able to demonstrate how to segment the data set into different actionable segments. This would not have been possible if we had employed the widely used traditional k -means algorithm. Finally, we are able to generate in-depth insights about how users engage and use social networks on an individual basis. This in effect could help businesses identify and formulate strategies to increase customer retention, increase sales and roll out marketing campaigns. For instance, if a social feature introduced shows a comparatively higher engagement among a group of users with respect to a particular feature, a business may imply that the feature is very useful for the group and use it as a basis to promote products to other groups who might have similar group characteristics.

This study provides a framework for studying user engagement, presenting a set of three dimensions for exploring user engagement on online social service (OSS) platforms. Using the specifics of a case study, we further demonstrate how the kernel k -means method surpasses the traditional k -means method in terms of performance, when analyzing high-dimensional big data sets on OSS platforms. Real data was utilized from an online social service platform, 7cot for our analysis. The study can be extended to develop frameworks to study other customer relations issues in other domain areas such as retail. We also intend to extend our study by delving deeper into other features and services that support user engagement on an OSS. The obvious challenge would be to maintain the generalizability of such an extension while maintaining its usability for specific purposes. The present work took into account the kernel k -means clustering method. Incorporating and devising different clustering methods and algorithms that work for different case scenarios would be another avenue for extending this study. The most general extension would be where the framework can itself decide on the kind of algorithm that would work, given the nature of data collected from the users. For example, the present dataset had heavy tails along all the nine features. A general framework would not only predict the kind of algorithm applicable based on the kind of data-set but would also offer insights on the profitability of the specific services offered by the website.

- Anderson, A. Huttenlocher D. and Kleinberg, J. (2012). Discovering Value from Community Activity on Focused Question Answering Sites: A Case Study of Stack Overflow. *Proceedings of the 18th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 850–858.
- Attfield, S. and Kazai, G. (2011). Towards a Science of User Engagement (Position Paper). *WSDM Workshop on User Modelling for Web Applications*. Retrieved from <http://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~mounia/Papers/engagement.pdf>
- Benevenuto, F., Rodrigues, T., Cha, M. and Almeida, V. (2009). Characterizing User Behavior in Online Social Networks. *Proceedings of the 9th ACM SIGCOMM Conference on Internet Measurement Conference*, (17313374869111495992related:ON2QmLZ2RfAJ), 49–62.
- Bergstra, J. and Bengio, Y. (2012). Random Search for Hyper-Parameter Optimization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13, 281–305.
- Booth, D. and Jansen, B. (2008). A Review of Methodologies for Analyzing Websites. *Handbook of Research on Web Log Analysis*, 141–162. Retrieved from http://faculty.ist.psu.edu/jjansen/academic/jansen_website_analysis.pdf
- Brooke, J. (1996). SUS-A Quick and Dirty Usability Scale. *Usability Evaluation in Industry*, 4–7.
- Camps-Valls, G., Rojo-Alvarez, J. L. and Martinez-Ramon, M. (2007). *Kernel Methods in Bioengineering, Signal and Image Processing*.
- Chang, H.-J., Hung, L.-P. and Ho, C.-L. (2007). An Anticipation Model of Potential Customers' Purchasing Behavior Based on Clustering Analysis and Association Rules Analysis. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 32(3), 753–764. Retrieved from <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0957417406000327>
- Chen, Y. Y., Lai, F. W., Goh, K. N. and Daud, S. C. (2013). The Effect of Integrating Social Plugins into e-Commerce Website: A Study on Online Consumer Behaviour. In *International Conference on Ubiquitous Information Management and Communication*. ACM (pp. 0–5). doi:10.1145/2448556.2448612
- Chitta, R., Jin, R., Havens, T. C. and Jain, A. K. (2014). Scalable Kernel Clustering: Approximate Kernel k-means. *arXiv*.
- Chu, C.-W., Holliday, J. D. and Willett, P. (2009). Effect of Data Standardization on Chemical Clustering and Similarity Searching. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 49(2), 155–61. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19434820>
- Chuang, H. H. C., Lu, G., Peng, D. X. and Heim, G. R. (2014). Impact of Value-Added Service Features in e-Retailing Processes: An Econometric Analysis of Web Site Functions. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 45(6), 1159–1186.
- Clauset, A., Shalizi, C. R. and Newman, M. E. J. (2009). Power-Law Distributions in Empirical Data. *SIAM Review*, 51(4), 661. doi:10.1137/070710111
- Cyr, D., Hassanein, K., Head, M. and Ivanov, A. (2007). The Role of Social Presence in Establishing Loyalty in e-Service Environments. *Interacting with Computers*, 19(1), 43–56. doi:10.1016/j.intcom.2006.07.010

- De la Torre, F. and Vinyals, O. (2007). Learning Kernel Expansions for Image Classification. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2007. CVPR '07. IEEE Conference on* (pp. 1–7).
- Doran, D., Yelne, S. and Massari, L. (2015). Stay Awhile and Listen: User Interactions in a Crowdsourced Platform Offering Emotional Support. *arXiv*.
- Farajian, M. and Mohammadi, S. (2010). Mining the Banking Customer Behavior Using Clustering and Association Rules Methods. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering*.
- Gagné, C. and Godin, G. (2005). Improving self-report measures of non-adherence to HIV medications. *Psychology & Health, 20*(6), 803–816. doi:10.1080/14768320500386441
- Gong, N. Z., Xu, W., Huang, L., Mittal, P., Stefanov, E., Sekar, V. and Song, D. (2012). Evolution of Social-Attribute Networks: Measurements, Modeling, and Implications using Google+. *Internet Measurement Conference*, 131–144. doi:10.1145/2398776.2398792
- Gummerus, J., Liljander, V., Pura, M. and Riel, A. Van. (2004). Customer Loyalty to Content-Based Web Sites: The Case of an Online Health-Care Service. *Journal of Services Marketing, 18*(3), 175–186.
- Harris, L. C. and Goode, M. M. H. (2004). The four levels of loyalty and the pivotal role of trust: a study of online service dynamics. *Journal of Retailing, 80*(2), 139–158.
- Hawkshead, J. and Krousel-Wood, M. A. (2007). Techniques for Measuring Medication Adherence in Hypertensive Patients in Outpatient Settings: Advantages and Limitations. *Disease Management and Health Outcomes, 15*(2), 109–118. Retrieved from <http://ideas.repec.org/a/wkh/dmhout/v15y2007i2p109-118.html>
- Huang, Z. and Benyoucef, M. (2013). From e-commerce to Social Commerce: A Close Look at Design Features. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications, 12*(4), 246–259. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2012.12.003>
- Ikehara, C. and Crosby, M. (2005). Assessing Cognitive Load with Physiological Sensors. *Proceedings of the 38th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 00*(C), 1–9.
- Jacques, R. D. (1996). *The Nature of Engagement and its Role in Hypermedia Evaluation and Design*. Retrieved from <http://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.336369>
- Jain, A. K. (2010). Data Clustering: 50 Years Beyond K-means. *Pattern Recognition Letters, 31*(8), 651–666. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2009.09.011>
- Kim, E. (2013). Everything You Wanted to Know about the Kernel Trick (But Were Too Afraid to Ask). Retrieved August 1, 2014, from http://www.eric-kim.net/eric-kim-net/posts/1/kernel_trick.html
- Kodinariya, T. M. and Makwana, P. R. (2013). Review on Determining Number of Cluster in K-Means Clustering. *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies, 1*(6), 90–95.
- Konradt, U. and Sulz, K. (2001). The Experience of Flow in Interacting with a Hypermedia Learning Environment. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia, 10*(1), 69–84. Retrieved from

http://www.editlib.org/index.cfm?fuseaction=Reader.ViewAbstract&paper_id=7992&from=NEWDL

- Kunegis, J., Lommatzsch, A. and Bauckhage, C. (2009). The Slashdot Zoo: Mining a social network with negative edges. *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on World Wide Web*, 741–750. doi:10.1145/1526709.1526809
- Kwak, H., Lee, C., Park, H. and Moon, S. (2010). What is Twitter , s Social Network or a News Media? *The International World Wide Web Conference Committee (IW3C2)*, 1–10.
- Lalmas, M., O'Brien, H. L. and Yom-Tov, E. (2013). Measuring User Engagement. In *Tutorials of the 22nd International World Wide Web Conference*.
- Lehmann, J., Lalmas, M., Yom-Tov, E. and Dupret, G. (2012). Models of user engagement. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 7379 LNCS, 164–175. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-31454-4_14
- Lima, A., Rossi, L. and Musolesi, M. (2014). Coding together at scale: GitHub as a collaborative social network. In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media, ICWSM 2014* (pp. 295–304). Retrieved from <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-84909956490&partnerID=tZOTx3y1>
- Lipsky, L. (2009). *Queueing theory : A Linear Algebraic Approach*. doi:10.1007/ 978-0-387-49706-8
- Mislove, A., Koppula, H. S., Gummadi, K. P., Druschel, P. and Bhattacharjee, B. (2008). Growth of the flickr social network. In *Proceedings of the first workshop on Online social networks - WOSP '08* (pp. 25–30). doi:10.1145/1397735.1397742
- Ogonowski, A., Montandon, A., Botha, E. and Reyneke, M. (2014). Should New Online Stores Invest in Social Presence Elements? The Effect of Social Presence on Initial Trust Formation. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(4), 482–491. doi:10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.03.004
- Pang-Ning, T., Steinbach, M. and Kumar, V. (2006). *Introduction to data mining. Library of Congress*. doi:10.1016/0022-4405(81)90007-8
- Romero, R., Iglesias, E. and Borrajo, L. (2014). A Linear-RBF Multikernel SVM to Classify Big Text Corpora. *BioMed Research International*. Retrieved from <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/bmri/aa/878291/>
- Seah, M. and Cairns, P. (2008). From Immersion to Addiction in Videogames. In *Proceedings of BCS HCI* (pp. 55–63). Retrieved from <http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/68181/>
- Shukla, S. and Naganna, S. (2014). A Review on K-means Data Clustering Approach. *International Journal of Information & Computation Technology*, 4(17), 1847–1860.
- Steinbach, M., Karypis, G. and Kumar, V. (2000). A Comparison of Document Clustering Techniques. *KDD Workshop on Text Mining*, 400, 1–2. doi:10.1109/ICCCYB.2008.4721382
- Szell, M. and Thurner, S. (2010). Measuring Social Dynamics in a Massive Multiplayer Online Game. *Social Networks*, 32(4), 313–329. doi:10.1016/j.socnet.2010.06.001

- Taniar, D. (2008). *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Technologies*. IGI Global.
- Torkjazi, M., Rejaie, R. and Willinger, W. (2009). Hot Today , Gone Tomorrow : On the Migration of MySpace Users. ... *of the 2nd ACM Workshop on Online ...*, 43–48. doi:10.1145/1592665.1592676
- Ugander, J., Karrer, B., Backstrom, L., Marlow, C. and Alto, P. (2011). The Anatomy of the Facebook Social Graph. *Arxiv Preprint arXiv, abs/1111.4*(July), 1–17. doi:10.1.1.31.1768
- Van Dam, J.-W. and van de Velden, M. (2014). Online Profiling and Clustering of Facebook Users. *Decision Support Systems*, 70, 60–72. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923614002796>
- Viswanath, B., Mislove, A., Cha, M. and Gummadi, K. P. (2009). On the Evolution of User Interaction in Facebook. *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM Workshop on Online Social Networks - WOSN '09*, 37. doi:10.1145/1592665.1592675
- Webster, J. and Ho, H. (1997). Audience Engagement in Multimedia Presentations. *ACM SIGMIS Database*, 28(2), 63–77.
- Zhong, C., Salehi, M., Shah, S., Cobzarenco, M., Sastry, N. and Cha, M. (2014). Social Bootstrapping : How Pinterest and Last . fm Social Communities Benefit by Borrowing Links from Facebook. *Www2014*, 305–314. doi:10.1145/2566486.2568031

ANNEXURE

Parallel_SI_index.R (Calculation of SI Index)

```
1) # Compute Si index for a given sigma and a particular K
2)
3) library(foreach)
4) library(doMC)
5) library(doParallel)
6) library(ROCR)
7) library(cluster)
8) library(kernlab)
9) cluster_size<-size(of_sm7_1_0.007) #array for number of elements in each cluster
10) clusts <-sort(unique(of_sm7_1_0.007)) #number of clusters
11) sigma_1<-0 #summation 1
12) sigma_2<-0 #summation 2
13) sigma<-0.007 #given sigma value
14) stopCluster(cl) #stop cluster if already running
15) cl<-makeCluster(37) #specify the number of clusters
16) registerDoParallel(cl) #do parallel computation
17) SIindex<-function(i) #function returning value of SI index for each element
17) {
18) cluster_size<-size(of_sm7_1_0.007)
19) clusts <-sort(unique(of_sm7_1_0.007))
20) sigma_1<-0
21) sigma_2<-0
22) sigma<-0.01
23) temp<-rep(20000000000,length(clusts)-1)#for choosing minimum value of b, temp is
    placeholder
24) for(j in 1:length(of_sm7_1_0.007)) #for a in Si index
25) {
26)   if((of_sm7_1_0.007[j]==of_sm7_1_0.007[i])&&(i!=j))
27)   {
```

```

28)  sigma_1<-sigma_1-2*exp(-dist(rbind(Part_matrix[i,],Part_matrix[j,]))/sigma*sigma)
29)  sigma_2<-sigma_2+exp(-dist(rbind(Part_matrix[j,],Part_matrix[j,]))/sigma*sigma)
30)  }
31)  }
32)  a<-(exp(-
      (dist(rbind(Part_matrix[i,],Part_matrix[i,]))/sigma*sigma))+sigma_1+sigma_2)/cluster_size[of_sm7_1_0.007[i]]
33)  sigma_1<-0
34)  sigma_2<-0
35)  for(k in 1:length(clusts)) #for b in SI index
36)  {
37)  if((k==of_sm7_1_0.007[i])) #skipping the same cluster points
38)  {
39)    next();
40)  }
41)  else
42)  {
43)    for(j in 1:length(of_sm7_1_0.007))
44)    {
45)      if(of_sm7_1_0.007[j]==k)
46)      {
47)        sigma_1<-sigma_1-2*exp(-
          dist(rbind(Part_matrix[i,],Part_matrix[j,]))/sigma*sigma)
48)        sigma_2<-sigma_2+exp(-dist(rbind(Part_matrix[j,],Part_matrix[j,]))/sigma*sigma)
49)      }
50)    }
51)  }
52)
53)  if(!(k==of_sm7_1_0.007[i]))
54)  temp[k]<-(exp(-
      dist(rbind(Part_matrix[i,],Part_matrix[i,]))/sigma*sigma)+sigma_1+sigma_2)/cluster_size[k]
55)  sigma_1<-0
56)  sigma_2<-0

```

```
57) }
58) b<-min(temp) #use minimum value of in temp array as value of b
59) return(b-a[1])/max(b,a[1]) #return value of b-a/max(b,a)
60) }
61)
62) store<-foreach(i = 1:length(of_sm7_1_0.007),.packages='kernlab') %dopar% SIindex(i)
    #list of values , to mean, use v<-mean(unlist(store))
63) registerDoSEQ() #unregistering the parallel backened
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About the Student

Nripesh Trivedi is currently pursuing Integrated Masters' Degree in Mathematics and Computing at Department of Mathematical Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology (Banaras Hindu University), Varanasi. His research interests' span across data mining, machine learning and data management systems. His past research experiences include working as a RA at EPFL, Knoesis and Polotsk State University. He is also a summer alumnus of Indian Academy of Sciences.